

FAKE EMOTION DETECTION

MARIEM REDA¹ · SHEREEN A.TAIE² · ENGY RAGAE³

¹Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence, Fayoum University, Egypt

²College of Informatics, Midocean University, Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence, Fayoum University

³Department of Basic Science, Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence, Fayoum University, Egypt

Received: Aug 18, 2025

Accepted: Sep 09, 2025

Published: Sep 19, 2025

Abstract— One of the most important topics in emotion detection is the ability to differentiate between real and fake emotions. Facial expressions provide a lot of information that reflects different emotional states, and they are the most significant nonverbal communication methods. Real and fake emotional discrimination enhances the user's experience in interactive systems and provides significant insights into security and various healthcare applications. This paper introduces a new model combining two convolutional neural networks (CNNs) designed for face landmark detection and image analysis. By merging these networks, the model outperforms current state-of-the-art algorithms in detecting fake emotions via facial expression. The proposed model is trained and validated on the SASE-FE dataset. Although fake emotions have been successfully identified in most research, there are variations in methodology, dataset, and approach. The proposed model achieves a high accuracy rate of 99%. The developed model demonstrates a significant improvement in accuracy and reliability

Keywords— CNN · Emotion Detection · Fake · Real · Facial expression ·

I. INTRODUCTION

Human faces convey crucial information for communication. Emotions and facial expressions can lead to misunderstandings in nonverbal communication between people. Human emotions are influenced by events that occur throughout the day and impact their mood.[1] People can comprehend each other's emotions, but it remains challenging for machines to distinguish between genuine and fake feelings. According to a recent study [2], HCI (human-computer interaction) is the essential communication between humans and computers that aids in developing artificial intelligence systems.

Detecting emotions is critical in multiple domains, including marketing to indicate customer satisfaction with the product, elections, and investigations to ascertain a suspect's guilt.

Emotions are categorized into six fundamental types: anger, disgust, happiness, sadness, contempt, and surprise, as identified by the renowned psychologist Paul Ekman. [3], recognized for his pioneering research on emotions and facial expressions. Based on some studies [4], some people may mask their feelings by using fake facial expressions. It is challenging to differentiate between real and fake feelings. Numerous machines and deep learning techniques are used to train and test datasets.

The purpose of machine learning and deep learning is to verify the highest possible accuracy. However, the effectiveness of the current techniques in identifying fake emotions is unsatisfactory [1]. In this paper, we propose significant contributions to CNN. Based on the above discussion, this work seeks to enhance classification results. The current work successfully classifies real and fake emotions using the proposed algorithm (CNN).

Several techniques have been developed to categorize fake emotions in recent years, including neural networks [2], RNN, and SVM [5]. Furthermore, deep learning models have played an important role in capturing the information required to recognize emotion. The related work section will go over the most recently created neural networks and SVM challenges.

This paper's contribution is introducing a new model that uses concatenation between two CNNs to recognize fake emotions. A CNN for landmarks, a CNN for images, and a 2-CNN are combined, which can improve feature extraction and outperform existing approaches in classification accuracy.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the recent related work in fake emotion detection. Section 3 presents the proposed system. Section 4 discusses experimental results. Section 5 introduces the conclusion.

II. RELATED WORK

This section examines previous techniques for detecting fake emotions. Various approaches are discussed, including feature extraction methods, machine learning models, and evaluation metrics, and we compare our work to existing methodologies. The techniques for detecting fake emotions can be divided into using machine learning algorithms and using deep learning algorithms.

A. Machine learning algorithms: -

- **Standard Support Vector Machine**

[5] A ranked SVM was proposed for detecting fake emotions. The SASE-FE database was used to test the model. It also includes a general model that classifies a single input and a more specific model that rates two videos. The most recent

multiscale CNN model for face detection includes Dlib and landmark localization using Kazemi and Sullivan. This model had the highest fake emotion detection accuracy (76%).

- **Enhanced Boosted Support Vector Machine (EBSVM)**

[1] EBSVM developed a model for detecting fake emotions by finding the threshold needed to discriminate between real and fake emotions. The model was trained using the FED database, which included photos of 50 people, and tested on the SASE-FE dataset. A concurrent cascade of linear regression algorithms is used to detect faces and localize landmarks. The highest accuracy achieved with this algorithm was 98.08%.

B. Deep learning techniques:

- **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs): -**

[7] Proposed a convolutional neural network model for detecting fake smiles with high precision. The model was trained on the FER-2013 database in seven emotions: happy, sad, disgusted, angry, fearful, surprised, and neutral, and then identified as a real or fake smile based on the recorded score and percentage of each emotion. The Viola-Jones algorithm determines both preprocessing and face detection. This article distinguishes between real and fake smiles using muscles around the eyes.

- **Long short-term memory networks (LSTMs): -**

A form of recurrent neural network designed for sequence data. LSTMs can learn long-term dependencies and are commonly employed in applications such as language modeling, speech recognition, and time series prediction.

[4] The proposed LSTM-PB combines mirror neuron modeling and deep recurrent neural networks with parametric bias (PB). The binary classifier is used to improve the discrimination capabilities of two PB vectors. Face detection is performed by combining Haar feature detection with the MOSSE-based object tracker and then extracting face landmarks using the Dlib library. Using this technique, the maximum accuracy was 66.7% when applied to the SASE-FE dataset.

[8] Several models were proposed; however, LSTM performed best in distinguishing real from fake smiles and conventional FER approaches for identifying faces and extracting features. The MAHNOB dataset served as the model's training data. The model was evaluated on SPOS and MMI with 87% and 97% accuracy, respectively.

- **Hybrid Approaches**

[9] shown that fake emotion detection across two modalities can be accomplished with deep learning, and more especially, CNN-LSTM architecture. Their Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) model outperformed earlier research by achieving 70% accuracy on the SASE-FE dataset. The Speech Emotion Recognition (SER) model, on the other hand, achieved a significantly better accuracy of 96.93%, indicating the great potential of vocal signals in differentiating between real and artificial emotions. Despite these promising findings, the study had many drawbacks, most notably the limited size of the SASE-FE dataset, which reduced the FER model's resilience and generalizability. Similarly, the use of two distinct speech datasets (acted vs. natural) raises problems about dataset compatibility and bias in classifying emotions as strictly real or artificial. The authors emphasized the critical necessity for a complete multimodal dataset that includes both genuine and fabricated emotions in facial and speech cues. Such a dataset would allow for more reliable and scalable models, indicating a promising area for future research in fake emotion detection.

Using a variety of assessment metrics, we analyze our model's performance and compare it with current methods. The results of this stage, which are our main objective, have been compared to the results of other cutting-edge models. The purpose of this comparison is to highlight how crucial it is to detect fake emotions. Additionally, our model's accuracy, dataset, and methodology have been compared to those of other models, such as the NIT-OVGU [5] teams and HCILab [4]. The comparative summary of the related works in fake emotion detection is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the related works in fake emotion detection

Author(s)	Year of Publication	Technique	Dataset	Accuracy
Annadurai, Swaminathan; Arock, Michael; A.Vadivel	2023	EBSVM	FED	98.08% in FED Dataset
Saxen, Frerk; Werner, Philipp; Al-Hamadi, Ayoub	2017	SVM	SASE-FE	76%

Kumar, G. A. Rajesh; Kumar, Ravi Kant; Sanyal, Goutam	2017	Long-term and short-term memory (LSTM) with parametric bias	SASE-FE	66.7%
Nguyen, Minh Tu; Nguyen, Quoc Khanh; Kazunori, Kotani; Siritanawan, Prarinya	2023	Bidirectional LSTM	MAHNOB dataset	87%
Omar Sameh Badr, Nada Ibrahim, Amr ElMougy	2023	CNN-LSTM (FER & SER)	SASE-FE (facial expressions), MSP-IMPROV (acted/fake speech), MSP-Podcast (natural/real speech)	FER: 70% SER: 96.93%

Table 1 shows that most existing research on emotion detection has concentrated on genuine emotions, with little attention to fake emotions. Current research frequently uses controlled datasets, and the majority of models are assessed using accuracy measures. Still, the explainability of predictions, which is essential for comprehending misleading behaviors, is not taken into account. After comparing techniques, deep learning is more effective at detecting real and fake emotions in complex data sets and automatically learning features from datasets. However, it requires more computational power and larger datasets for optimal performance[10][11]. Machine learning works better on smaller, less computationally demanding datasets since it is easier to use and more effective.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

For high-performance fake emotion detection and filtering, a new model was proposed that uses concatenation between two CNNs to enhance feature extraction and improve classification accuracy. This section will present an outline of the techniques and algorithms employed in our model. Figure 2 demonstrates the framework of the proposed model.

These models include three phases:

- A. Preprocessing.
- B. Feature Extraction.
- C. Classification.

These phases will be illustrated in detail in the following subsections.

Fig. 2. The framework of the proposed model.

A. PREPROCESSING

Preprocessing is a basic step to improve data quality and ensure its suitability for machine learning models. The preprocessing phase includes image framing, resizing, face detection, and landmark localization. The steps will be discussed in full detail below.

Framing: Each video is just a series of frames. Dividing videos into frames and extracting data by applying transformations to each frame. To cut down on redundancy and simplify computations, we convert the frames to grayscale.

Resizing: This is an important stage for adjusting the width and height of an image to reduce image size and speed up processing. We performed a resizer on the image to make it (64, 64).

Face detection: Human faces will be identified at this stage. Identifying human faces and determining their emotions is a crucial task. In every frame, the face is detected. **Landmark Localization:** Dlib's pre-trained Facial Landmark Detector Model was employed. Which can identify 68 2-dimensional points on the human face. It is made up of a collection of points with (x,y) coordinates on a human face [12]. The facial landmarks' coordinates are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 The 68 facial landmarks coordinate [12].

B. FEATURE EXTRACTION

CNNs use a convolutional structure to extract features from data before classification tasks. Convolutional layers are sometimes referred to as feature extractor layers. They are composed of a set of filters applied to entry data. These layers apply convolution operations using filters to detect patterns such as edges, corners, or textures in the input data. Features are retrieved from input data by assigning weights to height and width.

By using batching to divide data into epochs, a CNN model can be designed to extract key information and features while speeding up computation. In this stage, a CNN for landmarks extraction and a CNN for image analysis are performed. After that, the features from the two CNNs are combined to form a final representation of each face. In this section, we shall demonstrate layer by layer.

CNN for Image analysis:

Layer 1: The input layer, Input[64x64x3], will hold the raw pixel values of the image, in this case, a face image of the input layer, Input[64x64x3], will store the image's raw pixel values; for example, a face image with width 64, height 64-, and three-color channels are regarded as red, green, and blue.

Layer 2: A convolutional layer with 32 3*3 filters calculates the output of neurons in the input's associated regions, using the RELU activation function.

Layer 3: The output of neurons in the relevant input regions is calculated by a convolutional layer with 64 3x3 filters, and the RELU activation function is then applied.

Layer 4: The maximum POOL layer will minimize samples. This procedure occurs along the spatial dimensions of (2, 2) width and height.

Layer 5: The RELU activation function is applied to a convolutional layer with 128 3x3 filters, which computes the output of neurons in the relevant input areas [13].

Layer 6: The maximum POOL layer reduces samples. This procedure occurs at the width, height, and spatial sizes (2, 2).

Layer 7: The array will be transformed into a 1D array by the flattened layer.

Layer 8: Design a dense layer with 512 neurons and use the RELU activation function, followed by 0.5 dropout.

CNN for Landmarks extraction:

Layer 1: An input layer that expects to receive a 136-dimensional vector. This is most likely equal to 136 landmarks

Features

Layer 2: A dense layer with 128 neurons and a RELU activation function with a dropout of 0.5 was randomly dropped during training to minimize overfitting. This helps in finding complex patterns from the input data.

CLASSIFICATION

In this phase, we combined the output feature representation from two CNNs at the feature level using a concatenation operation to images and landmarks features with SoftMax activation to predict fake or real emotions.

Concatenation of 2_CNNs:

- Layer 1: The fully connected layer computes the class scores by concatenating the image output and landmarks output with 512 neurons, the RELU activation function, and 0.5 dropouts, and each neuron in this layer is connected to all of the values in the preceding neurons and softmax.
- Layer 2: Twelve neurons make up the softmax layer, which predicts 12 output classes.

Figure 4 illustrates the architecture of the proposed CNN, including the input layer, convolution layers, pooling layers, a flattening layer, and a fully connected layer.

Fig. 4. The architecture of the proposed model

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section will describe the experiment and give a detailed analysis of the findings. The experiment's phases were carried out on the SASE-FE database.

A. Dataset Description

The data set used is SASE-FE [14]. This dataset includes recordings from 50 participants aged 19 to 36 years, with a gender distribution of around 41% female and 59% male. The participants come from various ethnic backgrounds, with 77.8% Caucasian, 14.8% Asian, and 7.4% African, assuring a degree of demographic diversity. A total of 643 video clips were captured, each lasting between 3 and 4 seconds. The videos were captured with a GoPro Hero high-definition camera with a resolution of 1280×960 pixels and a frame rate of 100 frames per second (fps). Each recording begins with a neutral facial expression, then moves on to the desired emotion (whether genuine or unfelt), and finally returns to neutral.

The dataset includes six universal emotions: happiness, sadness, anger, disgust, contempt, and surprise. Each emotion is represented in two forms: real and fake, for a total of 12 emotion classes. This distinct architecture makes SASE-FE a challenging benchmark for both human perception studies and machine learning models, as unreal expressions are frequently subtle and difficult to distinguish from genuine ones.

Figure 5 displays a sample of the SASE-FE database is displayed.

Fig. 5. Sample of SASE-FE Dataset

B. Experimental Phase

This section discusses the experimental details and the results achieved in predicting fake emotions. The training work is carried out using the CNN model. The experiment has specific features and parameters. The experiments were conducted using Google Colab. Training the model across 10 epochs and analyzing the results. In each epoch, the dataset was trained by comparing the error to the expected output and adjusting weights and biases to reduce the loss function and achieve high accuracy. Table 2 shows the relationship between the loss function and accuracy during the training and validation phases. Table 3 summarizes the main specifications, such as model components, parameter settings, and other details, to give a complete overview of the proposed model. Careful consideration went into selecting these specifications to ensure optimal performance.

TABLE 2 DEMONSTRATES THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LOSS FUNCTION AND ACCURACY DURING THE TRAINING AND VALIDATION PHASES

Epoch	Loss		Accuracy	
	Training	Validation	Training	Validation
1	4.5450	0.7384	0.1455	0.7852
2	0.6987	0.1035	0.7608	0.9739
3	0.2247	0.0593	0.9224	0.9808
4	0.1419	0.0489	0.9514	0.9826
5	0.1080	0.0388	0.9618	0.9846
6	0.0911	0.0373	0.9672	0.9852
7	0.0768	0.0335	0.9719	0.9862
8	0.0683	0.0310	0.9744	0.9875
9	0.0615	0.0298	0.9767	0.9883
10	0.0551	0.0289	0.9788	0.9884

This table shows a considerable improvement in model performance across 10 epochs. The training loss starts out very high at 4.5450 and quickly drops to 0.0551, demonstrating that the model is learning successfully. The validation loss is low throughout. The training accuracy begins at 14.55%, which is fairly low, but gradually increases to 97.88%, indicating that the model is effectively learning the training patterns. The validation accuracy begins at 78.52%, which is already good, and rises to 98.84%, indicating strong performance on unknown data. The table indicates that the model performs well in both learning and generalisation, with no substantial overfitting during training and validation.

TABLE 3 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE PROPOSED MODEL.

Specification	Value
Size of training data	162038
Size of validation data	40510
Activation function for images	Relu
Activation function for landmarks	Relu
Activation function for output layers	Softmax
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.0001
Loss function	categorical_crossentropy
Sample test data path	1000
Number of epochs	10
Batch size	32

A comprehensive summary of the model's architecture and hyperparameters is given in this table. The model has enough data to learn from due to the large training dataset (162,038 samples), and its performance can be evaluated with the aid of the validation dataset (40,510 samples). For faster learning, ReLU activation is used for images and landmarks, whereas Softmax activation in the output layer is appropriate for multi-class classification. For adaptive learning, the Adam optimiser is a good choice, and stable convergence is guaranteed by the learning rate of 0.0001. A batch size of 32 guarantees effective processing, and 10 epochs allows the model to be appropriately trained without requiring an excessive amount of training time. The model's optimisation for multi-class classification is validated by the categorical cross-entropy loss function. Overall, this table illustrates well-considered design decisions that contribute to the model's high performance. When the loss function is high, the accuracy decreases. The x-axis shows the number of epochs, while the y-axis represents the accuracy and loss function obtained on the validated/test set. The proposed model prevents overfitting by reducing the number of epochs, which improves the model's ability to generalize to new data. These findings emphasize the significance of choosing an ideal number of epochs to balance learning efficiency. Figure 6 displays the loss function for each epoch; this graph illustrates how the loss function varies for both training and validation across the number of epochs. The X-axis shows the number of epochs. The loss value is represented by the Y-axis, which starts at about 1.75 and decreases to 0.0. The Blue Line (Training Loss): While the loss is large at first, suggesting high errors, it rapidly drops as the model learns, stabilising at a low value after a few epochs. The Orange Line (Validation Loss): This line shows a similar pattern, with the validation loss reducing as the model gets better while still being somewhat higher than the training loss. The model appears to have successfully reduced errors, as indicated by the extremely low final loss numbers.

The accuracy of the training and validation data varies with the number of epochs, as this graph illustrates. The number of epochs, or iterations, is shown by the X-axis. Accuracy is represented by the Y-axis, which ranges from 0.65 to 1.0.

Figure 7 shows the accuracy for each epoch.

Fig. 6. Loss curve over training epochs.

Fig. 7. Model accuracy during training and validation.

To gain more understanding of the model's decision boundaries and error modes, we examine the confusion matrix for our 12 emotion classes in Figure 8. In this matrix, each row represents the true label, and each column represents the predicted label. High values along the main diagonal indicate correct classifications, whereas off-diagonal entries show different patterns of misclassification.

Fig 8. Shows the Confusion Matrix Of The Model.

As shown in Figure 8, the confusion matrix is dominated by strong diagonal entries, confirming that the majority of test samples were allocated to the correct emotion class. Misclassifications are seldom and specific (for example, a single N2D image has been mistaken for D2N2Sur), indicating that the performance of the emotion classification model was assessed using a test dataset containing images of 12 emotions, making a few errors. This balanced result across all categories demonstrates the long-term impact of our approach.

classes. Precision, recall, and F1-score for each class were employed as evaluation metrics, along with overall accuracy, macro average, and weighted average. Table 4 provides the model's metrics.

Table 4 Shows the Model Metrics.

Emotion	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
D2N2Sur	0.98	1.00	0.99	79
H2N2A	1.00	0.96	0.98	91
H2N2C	0.97	0.98	0.97	87
H2N2D	0.97	0.98	0.97	89
H2N2S	1.00	1.00	1.00	86
N2A	1.00	1.00	1.00	77
N2C	0.97	1.00	0.98	92
N2D	1.00	0.98	0.99	82
N2H	0.99	1.00	0.99	82
N2S	1.00	0.97	0.99	77
N2Sur	1.00	1.00	1.00	75
S2N2H	1.00	1.00	1.00	75
Accuracy			0.99	992
Macro avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	992
Weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	992

The findings are summarized in the table above, which shows that the model achieved high performance, with an overall accuracy of 99%. All individual classes showed F1 scores ranging from 0.97 to 1.00, confirming the model's ability to reliably distinguish between various emotional states.

For example, the classification of the "D2N2Sur" class had a precision of 0.98, a recall of 1.00, and an F1-score of 0.99, indicating extremely few misclassifications. Several classes, including "N2A," "N2H," and "S2N2H," achieved perfect scores (accuracy = 1.00, recall = 1.00, F1-score = 1.00), demonstrating the model's robustness on those specific emotion categories.

The macro and weighted averages for precision, recall, and F1-score were all 0.99, demonstrating that the model performed demonstrating its ability to recognize fake emotions. When the face's features and landmarks are retrieved from the original frame, the CNN network can determine the frame's label consistently across all classes, regardless of class imbalance.

To evaluate the proposed model's effectiveness, its performance was compared with various previous models on the same dataset (SASE-FE). Table 5 summarizes the findings, demonstrating the accuracy obtained by various methodologies throughout time. This comparison shows that the proposed Combined 2-CNN model outperforms previous approaches for detecting fake emotions.

Table 5: Fake Emotion Detection Models' Performance Comparison (SASE-FE)

Author(s)	Year	Technique	Dataset	Accuracy
Saxen, Frerk; Werner, Philipp; Al-Hamadi, Ayoub	2017	SVM	SASE-FE	76%
Kumar, G. A. Rajesh; Kumar, Ravi Kant; Sanyal, Goutam	2017	LSTM with parametric bias	SASE-FE	66.7%
Badr, Omar Sameh; Ibrahim, Nada; ElMougy, Amr	2023	CNN-LSTM (FER & SER)	SASE-FE, MSP-IMPROV, MSP-Podcast	FER: 70%, SER: 96.93%
Proposed Model	2025	Combined 2-CNN	SASE-FE	99%

Table 5 shows a comparison of the proposed model and earlier published techniques on the SASE-FE dataset. As demonstrated, Saxen et al. (2017) achieved 76% accuracy with a traditional SVM classifier, but Kumar et al. (2017) achieved 66.7% accuracy with an LSTM model with parametric bias. Badr et al. (2023) used CNN-LSTM architectures to achieve 70% accuracy for facial expression recognition (FER) and 96.93% for speech emotion recognition (SER). In contrast, the suggested Combined 2-CNN model outperformed all previous techniques on the SASE-FE dataset, with an overall accuracy of 99%.

This significant improvement demonstrates the effectiveness of using deep convolutional networks to capture discriminative facial emotion variables, and it proves that the suggested approach is more robust and reliable than previous models.

A bar chart was used to illustrate the performance of various models in addition to the tabular comparison, as seen in Figure 9. The performance difference between hybrid models (CNN-LSTM), conventional machine learning techniques (SVM, LSTM), and the suggested Combined 2-CNN model is easier to see according to this graphical representation. As the chart makes evident, the suggested model outperformed previous techniques by achieving the best accuracy.

Figure 9. Detecting Fake Emotions: Model Accuracy Results

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the proposed model investigated the challenge of fake emotion detection, which is difficult but necessary in many domains, such as human-computer interaction, psychology, and security. The proposed model findings emphasize the importance of utilizing machine learning and deep learning to differentiate genuine emotions. The proposed model implemented a convolutional neural network and trained it for 10 epochs. The model was designed to extract deep features from input images, utilizing multiple convolutional layers. The training process was observed to make sure the model distinguishes features efficiently and with the least amount of overfitting. Using SASE-FE datasets, the proposed model successfully identified fake and real emotions and predicted the label of an input frame. On the testing dataset, the proposed model achieved an accuracy of 99%.

One major strength of this study is that the proposed methodology outperformed previous approaches used on the same dataset. This demonstrates the model's robustness and improved ability to differentiate between genuine and fake emotions. This work demonstrates stronger generalization and provides a more reliable foundation for future applications in fake emotion detection.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Annadurai, M. Arock, and A. Vadivel, "Real and fake emotion detection using enhanced boosted support vector machine algorithm Content courtesy of Springer Nature; terms of use apply. Rights reserved. Content courtesy of Springer Nature, terms of use apply. Rights reserved .," pp. 1333–1353, 2023.
- [2] N. A. S. Badrulhisham and N. N. A. Mangshor, "Emotion Recognition Using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)," J. Phys. Conf. Ser., vol. 1962, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1962/1/012040.
- [3] W. K. Ngai, H. Xie, D. Zou, and K. L. Chou, "Emotion recognition based on convolutional neural networks and heterogeneous bio-signal data sources," Inf. Fusion, vol. 77, no. May 2021, pp. 107–117, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.inffus.2021.07.007.
- [4] G. A. R. Kumar, R. K. Kumar, and G. Sanyal, "Discrimination between Genuine Versus Fake Emotion Using Long-Short Term Memory with Parametric Bias and Facial Landmarks," Proc. - 2017 IEEE Int. Conf. Comput. Vis. Work. ICCVW 2017, vol. 2018-Janua, pp. 3065–3072, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ICCVW.2017.362.
- [5] F. Saxen, P. Werner, and A. Al-Hamadi, "Real vs. Fake Emotion Challenge: Learning to Rank Authenticity from Facial Activity Descriptors," Proc. - 2017 IEEE Int. Conf. Comput. Vis. Work. ICCVW 2017, vol. 2018-Janua, no. November, pp. 3073–3078, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ICCVW.2017.363.
- [7] G. A. R. Kumar, R. K. Kumar, and G. Sanyal, "Discriminating real from fake smile using a convolutional neural network," ICCIDS 2017 - Int. Conf. Comput. Intell. Data Sci. Proc., vol. 2018-Janua, pp. 1–6, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ICCIDS.2017.8272651.
- [8] M. T. Nguyen, Q. K. Nguyen, K. Kazunori, and P. Siritanawan, "Towards recognizing facial expressions at a deeper level: Discriminating genuine and fake smiles from a sequence of images," Proc. - 2019 6th NAFOSTED Conf. Inf. Comput. Sci. NICS 2019, no. June, pp. 387–392, 2019, doi: 10.1109/NICS48868.2019.9023790.
- [9] O. S. Badr, N. Ibrahim, and A. ElMougy, "Fake Emotion Detection Using Affective Cues and Speech Emotion Recognition for Improved Human Computer Interaction," 2023 2nd International Conference on Smart Cities 4.0, Cairo, Egypt, 2023, pp. 559-564.
- [10] Zhao, Y., Yi, J., Tao, J., Wang, C., Zhang, X., & Dong, Y.2022. EmoFake: An Initial Dataset for Emotion Fake Audio Detection. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-8367-0_25
- [11] N. Bhakt, P. Joshi, and P. Dhyani, "A Novel Framework for Real and Fake Smile Detection from Videos," 2018 Second International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA), Coimbatore, India, 2018, pp. 1327-1330.
- [12] C. Sagonas, G. Tzimiropoulos, S. Zafeiriou, and M. Pantic, "300 faces in-the-wild challenge: The first facial landmark Localization Challenge," Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Comput. Vis., pp. 397–403, 2013, doi: 10.1109/ICCVW.2013.59.
- [13] Karlik, B., & Olgac, A. V. (2011). Performance analysis of various activation functions in generalized MLP architectures of neural networks. International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Expert Systems, 1(4), 111–122.
- [14] K. Kulkarni, C. A. Corneanu, I. Ofodile, S. Escalera, X. Baró, S. Hyniewska, J. Allik, and G. Anbarjafari, "Automatic Recognition of Facial Displays of Unfelt Emotions," IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 377–390, Apr.–Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TAFFC.2018.2874987.